

Ultrasound imaging for measuring muscle and subcutaneous fat tissue thickness of the anterior thigh: a 2 year longitudinal study in middle age

Filippo Mechelli^{1,2*}, Lars Arendt-Nielsen¹, Maria Stokes^{3,4} & Sandra Agyapong-Badu⁵

¹Centre of Sensory Motor Interaction, Department of Health Science and Technology, School of Medicine, University of Aalborg, Aalborg, Denmark, ²Private Practice, Urbino, Italy, ³School of Health Sciences, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK, ⁴Centre for Sport, Exercise and Osteoarthritis Versus Arthritis, Nottingham, UK, ⁵School of Sport, Exercise and Rehabilitation Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK

Abstract

Background Ultrasound (US) imaging technique is widely used in research and clinical settings to assess the morphology and morphometry of neuromusculoskeletal structures. The technique has reported validity and reliability in measuring the size of various muscles under controlled conditions. The aim of the present study was to assess anterior thigh thickness using US imaging, in a healthy cohort of middle-aged older adults.

Methods Participants included 17 healthy older adults involved in regular moderate-vigorous activities (age range 39–66 years). US imaging scans of the anterior thighs 2 years since baseline measurements were performed. Images were analysed offline to compare US imaging measurements of muscle thickness and subcutaneous fat (SF) of the anterior thigh taken at baseline and after 2 years.

Results There was no significant difference between muscle thickness measurements taken at baseline and after 2 years (mean, standard deviation; baseline = 2.80 ± 0.71 cm; follow-up = 2.77 ± 0.72 cm, $P = 0.33$). There was also no significant change in SF thickness (baseline = 1.04 ± 0.41 cm; follow-up = 1.06 ± 0.40 , $P = 0.33$).

Conclusions The results show that there was no decline in anterior thigh muscle thickness or increase in SF in the healthy cohort studied using US imaging over a 2 year period. These findings demonstrate the robustness of US imaging measurements over time.

Keywords Cohort study; Muscle thickness; Rectus femoris; Ultrasound imaging; Subcutaneous fat thickness; Vastus intermedius

*Correspondence to: Filippo Mechelli, Private Practice, 61029, Urbino, Italy. Email: fmechelli@gmail.com

Introduction

The use of ultrasound (US) imaging in research and clinical settings to assess morphology and morphometry of neuromusculoskeletal structures is increasingly gaining acceptance.¹ An objective measure of muscle thickness, cross-sectional area, volume, fibres length, and pennation angle provides the opportunity to obtain an indirect evaluation of muscle function and strength.² US imaging of skeletal muscles carries the advantage of providing a rapid, non-invasive, portable, safe, and clinically useful method of obtaining objective measurements.

The US imaging technique is operator-dependent,³ so user repeatability of measurements need to be examined for muscle and perimuscular tissues.¹ The potential to use US for accurate and reliable measurement of muscle thickness as well as of non-contractile tissues is important for researchers and clinicians. Measurement of muscle characteristics longitudinally would be potentially useful to monitor changes with ageing. Agyapong-Badu *et al.*⁴ used US imaging to provide objective data on the effects of ageing and gender on relative anterior thigh thickness in healthy people. The authors also reported high intra-rater reliability for the measurements [ICC values from 0.88 for muscle thickness

to 0.97 for subcutaneous fat (SF) thickness]. Recently, intra-rater and inter-rater reliability of US measurements of muscle and SF thickness of the anterior thigh were reported by Mechelli *et al.*⁵ in a healthy middle-aged cohort (intra-rater reliability ICC3,2 of 0.96 for muscle thickness, 0.99 for SF; inter-rater reliability ICC3,1 of 0.98 for muscle thickness, 0.81 for SF). Whittaker and Emery⁶ have also reported excellent intra-rater reliability of US for measuring the vastus medialis muscle thickness (ICC values above 0.90). Regarding validity, muscle thickness measurements on US images were not significantly different to those obtained using magnetic resonance imaging, demonstrating criterion validity, for some muscles in the lower-limbs, including vastus medialis,⁷ rectus femoris and vastus intermedius,⁸ and anterior hip muscles.⁹

Quadriceps muscle atrophy is common in patients with knee osteoarthritis¹⁰ and other painful knee conditions.^{11,12} Sudden muscle atrophy is almost an unavoidable consequence in critically ill patients in intensive care units.^{13–17} Objective assessment of muscle thickness at the bedside could be a useful marker for clinicians to assess relative contributions of muscle and fat and balance nutritional support to attenuate such muscle mass loss.

Loss of muscle mass occurs over time with ageing due to sarcopenia¹⁸ and also cachexia in chronic conditions.¹⁹ Approximately 24–27% of muscle mass is lost between the second and seventh decades.²⁰ The functional consequences of sarcopenia include loss of mobility and physical independence.²¹ Identifying robust ways of detecting changes in muscle in middle age may help to prevent premature frailty. Ultrasound studies of changes with age involve cross-sectional comparisons between age groups but documenting changes longitudinally in the same individuals appear to be lacking. It would be particularly helpful to know about the status of muscle changes in middle age, at the time when osteoarthritis commonly starts, so that the relative effects of joint disease and ageing on muscle size could be better understood.

The purpose of the present study, the first to our knowledge, was to evaluate US imaging measurements of anterior thigh thickness (quadriceps muscle and non-contractile tissue), in a healthy middle-aged cohort at baseline and at 2 year follow-up to assess changes over time.

The null hypothesis was that there would be no difference between US imaging measurements of anterior thigh SF tissue and muscle thickness taken at baseline and those after a 2 year follow-up in a healthy middle-aged cohort.

Materials and methods

Participants

Seventeen (9 females and 8 males) healthy, moderately active adults,²² aged 51.58 ± 10.29 (39–66) years (see *Table 1*

Table 1 Participant characteristics

Variable	Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i> = 17)	
	Baseline	2 year follow-up
Age (years)	49.6 \pm 10.3	51.6 \pm 10.3
Height (m)	1.7 \pm 0.1	1.7 \pm 0.1
Body mass (kg)	71.5 \pm 12.2	72.0 \pm 13.7
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.2 \pm 3.8	24.3 \pm 4.2

SD, standard deviation; BMI, body mass index.

for other characteristics), underwent US imaging of their anterior thighs. The measurements were performed at baseline and at 2 year follow-up. The 2 year follow-up period was chosen as the minimum length of time to enable changes in muscle thickness to occur, as it is known that after the age of 50 years, muscle mass decreases at an annual rate of approximately 1–2%.²³ Exclusion criteria applied were similar to that reported in Mechelli *et al.*⁵ to exclude conditions that affect muscle function and a variation in diet and nutritional habits and/or in amount of weekly physical activity since baseline assessment. The investigator notified participants to refrain from vigorous exercise within the preceding 24 h to study participation.

Ultrasound imaging measurements

An ultrasound scanner (MyLab25; Esaote, Genova, Italia) with a 7.5 MHz linear transducer (40 mm length) was used to obtain images of the anterior thigh. Ultrasound scans, both baseline and at follow-up, were acquired in the same setting with the participant in supine lying position with the knee fully extended and weight bags placed around the feet to keep hip in a neutral position and ankles relaxed in a slight plantar flexion (*Figure 1*). B-mode transverse scans were obtained at two thirds of the distance measured from the antero-superior iliac spine to the superior pole of patella.^{5,8,24} The scanning site was marked with a skin-marking pen. During image acquisition, the transducer was coated with a generous amount of ultrasound water-based transmission gel and was placed perpendicular to the skin applying the lightest contact pressure to ensure that underlying tissues were not compressed.^{5,8} Scanner parameters remained the same for all measurements, ensuring uniformity to the baseline measurements procedure. The same investigator (F. M.) with established reliability for the technique took all scans.⁵ The between-day reliability was excellent (intraclass-correlation coefficients, ICC3,2, were 0.96 for muscle and 0.98 for SF). The minimal detectable change (MDC) from the reliability data for examining the precision of measurements was 3.6 mm for muscle thickness and 1.3 mm for SF.

Figure 1 The experimental set-up with a participant in supine lying. Placement of ultrasound transducer during image acquisition of anterior mid-thigh.

Ultrasound imaging data processing

US images were analysed offline to compare the measurements taken at baseline and follow-up using ImageJ software (available from <https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>). Each anonymized US scan was measured twice by the investigator (F. M.) and the mean used in the analysis. SF thickness was the distance from the skin to the outside edge of the superficial fascial layer, muscle thickness of rectus femoris and vastus intermedius were considered as the distance between the inside edges of each muscle border excluding perimascular fascia (Figure 2).

Data analysis

SPSS 22 (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL) was used to analyse the data. Normal distribution of the data was confirmed using the Shapiro–Wilk test.

Paired sample *t*-tests were used to assess differences between baseline and follow-up measurements. The alpha level was set at $P < 0.05$.²⁵

Results

The mean follow-up time was 26.55 ± 0.65 (25.92–28.81) months. There were no significant differences between muscle thickness ($P = 0.33$) and SF tissue ($P = 0.33$) measurements taken at baseline and at follow-up (Table 2). The difference in mean muscle thickness over the 2 year period (0.3 mm) was

Figure 2 Ultrasound scan of the anterior thigh showing subcutaneous fat (SF), rectus femoris (RF), and vastus intermedius (VI).

below the MDC of 3.6 mm reported previously in the same cohort.⁵ Similarly, the difference in SF (0.2 mm) was below the MDC of 1.3 mm.

Discussion

The present findings demonstrated that in the healthy middle-aged participants studied, there was no decline in quadriceps muscle thickness or increase in SF tissue that might be expected with advancing age.⁴ The null hypothesis of no difference in US imaging measurements of SF tissue and muscle thickness of the anterior thigh taken at baseline and at 2 year follow-up in a healthy middle-aged cohort was accepted. In addition to there being no statistically significant changes, differences in muscle and SF thickness at follow-up were within MDC from reliability testing,⁵ indicating that the difference was within the error of measurement and there was no real change over time. This consistency of measurements is important to demonstrate, as some measures can be statistically different over time but may not be clinically relevant if they are still within the MDC values. The consistency in muscle and SF thickness measurements demonstrates the robustness of US imaging measurements over the 2 year follow-up period in a healthy middle-aged cohort.

The combined loss of strength and impaired physical performance is frequently reported in older people as a consequence of sarcopenia.^{18,20,21,26} Loenneke *et al.*²⁷ proposed using US imaging in addition to dual X-ray absorptiometry to assess quadriceps muscle characteristics for early diagnosis of sarcopenia. The technique has been used to monitor lean

Table 2 Mean differences in anterior thigh thickness using paired sample *t*-tests

Anterior thigh measurements	Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i> = 17)				
	Baseline	2 year follow-up	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P</i> -value
Muscle thickness (mm)	28 \pm 7.1	27.7 \pm 7.2	0.98	33	0.33
Subcutaneous fat (mm)	10.4 \pm 4.1	10.6 \pm 4.0	-0.97	33	0.33

SD, standard deviation; *df*, degrees of freedom.

mass loss at the bedside in critically ill patients who experience quadriceps and skeletal muscle atrophy at a very early stage especially critically ill children.²⁸ Clinicians can utilize objective data from US imaging to administer an appropriate metabolic support to improve muscle morphology and subsequently function.^{14,16,29} The authors believe that monitoring both muscle and subcutaneous thickness to assess their relative contributions is important.

The sensitivity of the US imaging technique for assessing anterior thigh thickness over a longer period could be valuable for longitudinal assessment of the effects of nutrition during different diet protocols or weight loss/gain programmes. For instance, the effects of amino acid or other metabolic supplementation for quadriceps wasting in patients with knee osteoarthritis¹⁰ or other painful knee conditions.^{11,12} Another potential use of US could be to assess skeletal muscle atrophy for astronauts due to prolonged exposure to microgravity.³⁰ Indeed, such a longitudinal study is ongoing at the International Space Station (<https://ltda.jsc.nasa.gov/Experiment/exper/13941>), so the present results provide useful comparative data in terms of the expected consistency of quadriceps thickness throughout the 1 year period of the project, involving middle-aged astronauts rather than the young and older age ranges that are typically included in ageing studies.

Longitudinal assessment of the lower-limb muscles could be potentially useful for research on athletes and in sports settings, monitoring the effects of exercise interventions/training on quadriceps muscle mass and SF tissue and helping to assess the type and dose of exercise that optimizes muscle hypertrophy and/or a decrease of SF.

Furthermore, the robustness of US imaging measurements over time can be valuable for longitudinally evaluating quadriceps thickness after knee arthroplasty, anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction, and in general after surgical knee or hip procedures where muscle wasting may persist post-operatively.³¹

A limitation of US muscle thickness measurements is the inability to measure the contribution of the fatty infiltration that occurs with ageing.²¹ Likewise with some neuromuscular disorders, US thickness measurements need to be reported with caution, such as in Duchenne muscular dystrophy, which involves progressive atrophy of the skeletal muscles, together with a phenomenon known as pseudo hypertrophy, involving enlargement of muscles due to a replacement by connective tissue or fatty infiltration. In such cases, US imaging can be

used to assess tissue quality, using specific techniques, such as grayscale analysis of echogenicity.³² The technique has been used to assess diaphragm thickness in Duchenne muscular dystrophy patients with the potential to monitor disease progression.³³

The reliability of US imaging of muscle is well established,¹ and the contribution of the present study was to demonstrate the robustness of US imaging measurements of the anterior thigh over a longer period of time (2 years), extending the use of ultrasound from research during observational cross-sectional studies to longitudinal studies.

Conclusions

The present findings indicate that there was no statistically significant decline in muscle thickness or increase in anterior thigh SF tissue in a healthy cohort of middle-aged adults using US imaging over a 2 year follow-up period. These novel findings also demonstrate the robustness of US measurements over time.

Ethical considerations

The authors certify that they comply with the ethical guidelines for authorship and publishing of the *Journal of Cachexia, Sarcopenia and Muscle - Clinical Reports* (von Haehling S, Ebner N, Morley JE, Coats AJS, Anker SD. Ethical guidelines for authorship and publishing in the *Journal of Cachexia, Sarcopenia and Muscle - Clinical Reports*. *J Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle Clinical Reports* 2016; 1:e28:1-2). This study has been approved by the appropriate Ethics Committee and have therefore been performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments. All participants gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Whittaker JL, Teyhen DS, Elliott JM, Cook K, Langevin HM, Dahl HH, et al. Rehabilitative ultrasound imaging: understanding the technology and its applications. *J Orthop Sport Phys* 2007;**37**:434–449.
- Lieber RL. *Skeletal muscle structure and function: implications for rehabilitation and sports medicine*. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins; 1992.
- Wakefield RJ, Balint PV, Szkudlarek M, Filippucci E, Backhaus M, D'Agostino M-A, et al. Musculoskeletal ultrasound including definitions for ultrasonographic pathology. *J Rheumatol* 2005;**32**:2485–2487.
- Agyapong-Badu S, Warner M, Samuel D, Narici M, Cooper C, Stokes M. Anterior thigh composition measured using ultrasound imaging to quantify relative thickness of muscle and non-contractile tissue: a potential biomarker for musculoskeletal health. *Physiol. Meas* 2014;**35**:2165–2176.
- Mechelli F, Arendt-Nielsen L, Stokes M, Agyapong-Badu S. Inter-rater and intra-rater reliability of ultrasound imaging for measuring quadriceps muscle and non-contractile tissue thickness of the anterior thigh. *Biomed Phys Eng Express* 2019;**5**:037002.
- Whittaker JL, Emery CA. Sonographic measures of the gluteus medius, gluteus minimus, and vastus medialis muscles. *J Orthop Sport Phys* 2014;**44**:627–632.
- Worsley PR, Kitsell F, Samuel D, Stokes M. Validity of measuring distal vastus medialis muscle using rehabilitative ultrasound imaging versus magnetic resonance imaging. *Man Ther* 2014;**19**:259–263.
- Mechelli F, Arendt-Nielsen L, Stokes M, Agyapong-Badu S. Validity of ultrasound imaging versus magnetic resonance imaging for measuring anterior thigh muscle, subcutaneous fat, and fascia thickness. *Methods Protoc* 2019;**2**:58.
- Mendis MD, Wilson SJ, Stanton W, Hides JA. Validity of real-time ultrasound imaging to measure anterior hip muscle size: a comparison with magnetic resonance imaging. *J Orthop Sport Phys* 2010;**40**:577–581.
- Petterson SC, Barrance P, Buchanan T, Binder-Macleod S, Snyder-Mackler L. Mechanisms underlying quadriceps weakness in knee osteoarthritis. *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc.* 2008;**40**:422–427.
- Henriksen M, Rosager S, Aaboe J, Graven-Nielsen T, Bliddal H. Experimental knee pain reduces muscle strength. *J. Pain* 2011;**12**:460–467.
- Rice DA, McNair PJ, Lewis GN, Dalbeth N. Quadriceps arthrogenic muscle inhibition: the effects of experimental knee joint effusion on motor cortex excitability. *Arthritis Res Ther* 2014;**16**.
- Hadda V, Khilnani GC, Kumar R, Dhungana A, Mittal S, Khan MA, et al. Intra- and inter-observer reliability of quadriceps muscle thickness measured with bedside ultrasonography by critical care physicians. *Indian J. Crit. Care Med* 2017;**21**:448–452.
- Galindo Martín CA, Monares Zepeda E, Lescas Méndez OA. Bedside ultrasound measurement of rectus femoris: a tutorial for the nutrition support clinician. *J Clin Nutr Metab* 2017;**2017**:1–5.
- Toledo DO, Silva DC, Santos DM, Freitas BJ, Dib R, Cordioli RL, et al. Bedside ultrasound is a practical measurement tool for assessing muscle mass. *Rev Bras Ter Intensiva* 2017;**29**.
- Tillquist M, Kutsogiannis DJ, Wischmeyer PE, Kummerlen C, Leung R, Stollery D, et al. Bedside ultrasound is a practical and reliable measurement tool for assessing quadriceps muscle layer thickness. *J Parenter Enteral Nutr* 2014;**38**:886–890.
- Puthuchearu ZA, Rawal J, McPhail M, Connolly B, Ratnayake G, Chan P, et al. Acute skeletal muscle wasting in critical illness. *JAMA* 2013;**310**:1591.
- Rosenberg IH. Sarcopenia: origins and clinical relevance. *J Nutr* 1997;**127**:990S–991S.
- Aversa Z, Costelli P, Muscaritoli M. Cancer-induced muscle wasting: latest findings in prevention and treatment. *Ther Adv Med Oncol* 2017;**9**:369–382.
- Janssen I, Heymsfield SB, Wang Z, Ross R. Skeletal muscle mass and distribution in 468 men and women aged 18–88 yr. *J Appl Physiol* 2000;**89**:81–88.
- Narici MV, Maffulli N. Sarcopenia: characteristics, mechanisms and functional significance. *Br. Med. Bull* 2010;**95**:139–159.
- Physical Activity Guidelines Advisory Committee. *Physical activity guidelines advisory committee scientific report. Part C-7*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services 2018 https://health.gov/paguidelines/second-edition/report/pdf/pag_advisory_committee_report.pdf.
- von Haehling S, Morley JE, Anker SD. An overview of sarcopenia: facts and numbers on prevalence and clinical impact. *Journal of Cachexia, Sarcopenia and Muscle* 2010;**1**:129–133.
- Delaney S, Worsley P, Warner M, Taylor M, Stokes M. Assessing contractile ability of the quadriceps muscle using ultrasound imaging. *Muscle Nerve* 2010;**42**:530–538.
- Tenny S, Abdelgawad I. Statistical significance. In *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2019.
- Cruz-Jentoft AJ, Baeyens JP, Bauer JM, Boirie Y, Cederholm T, Landi F, et al. Sarcopenia: European consensus on definition and diagnosis: Report of the European Working Group on Sarcopenia in Older People. *Age Ageing* 2010;**39**:412–423.
- Loenneke JP, Thiebaut RS, Abe T. Estimating Site-specific muscle loss: a valuable tool for early sarcopenia detection? *Rejuvenation Res* 2014;**17**:496–498.
- Valla FV, Young DK, Rabilloud M, Periasami U, John M, Baudin F, et al. Thigh ultrasound monitoring identifies decreases in quadriceps femoris thickness as a frequent observation in critically ill children. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2017;**18**:e339–e347.
- Looijaard WGP, Molinger J, Weijs PJM. Measuring and monitoring lean body mass in critical illness. *Curr Opin Crit Care* 2018;**24**:241–247.
- Narici MV, de Boer MD. Disuse of the musculo-skeletal system in space and on earth. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 2011;**111**:403–420.
- Reardon K, Galea M, Dennett X, Choong P, Byrne E. Quadriceps muscle wasting persists 5 months after total hip arthroplasty for osteoarthritis of the hip: a pilot study. *Intern Med J* 2001;**31**:7–14.
- Harris-Love MO, Seamon BA, Teixeira C, Ismail C. Ultrasound estimates of muscle quality in older adults: reliability and comparison of Photoshop and ImageJ for the grayscale analysis of muscle echogenicity. *PeerJ* 2016;**4**:e1721.
- Laviola M, Priori R, D'Angelo MG, Aliverti A. Assessment of diaphragmatic thickness by ultrasonography in Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) patients. *PLoS One* 2018;**13**:e0200582.